

Event metadata

Event title	Using in silico design methods to create de novo proteins that selectively modulate apoptosis
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	16 September 2025
Time of event	12pm AEST
Topic description	<p>This webinar is part of the series “Leveraging deep learning to design custom protein-binding proteins”.</p> <p>Deep learning methods are speeding up the process of designing proteins with desirable biophysical properties. This fast moving field leverages computational workflows that integrate deep learning models like RFDiffusion, ProteinMPNN, Bindcraft with protein structural prediction methods (AlphaFold, Chai-1, Boltz-2) and traditional structural biology methods to improve protein design success rates.</p> <p>This webinar series features case studies from leaders in the field and is designed to inspire and help you recognise potential applications of this new approach to the design of protein-binding-proteins. Join us to hear how software such as Bindcraft is being applied to different research questions and gain hints and tips on using them in your own work.</p> <p>This series is brought to you by the Community for Structural Biology Computing in Australia.</p>
Speakers	Dr Richard Birkinshaw, WEHI
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/protein-binder-series
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	otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Structural biology http://edamontology.org/topic_1317 Protein interactions http://edamontology.org/topic_0128 AI Deep learning
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	These webinars are intended for structural biologists but are suitable for anyone who is curious about <i>de novo</i> protein design.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	By the end of this webinar you should be able to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe a use case of deep learning in the design of custom protein-binding-proteins
Training materials	Materials shared in this Zenodo record: Birkinshaw_slides_2025 (PDF): Slides presented during the webinar Materials shared elsewhere: A recording of this webinar is available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel: https://youtu.be/9-3sHy1ybpE